

1 LIGHT (TNFSF14) and a receptor for LIGHT (TNFRSF14) are associated with penetrating (fistulizing)
2 disease.

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Characteristic changes in TNFSF14 and TNFRSF14 were observed both in penetrating-type inflammatory
bowel disease and in humans with multiple sclerosis.